

Randomness-Based Saliency Arising in Naturally Designed Scene

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Abstract: A new framework is presented for contextual analysis of naturally designed scenes. In this framework, the random distribution of the scale-chromatic complexity is captured as environmental saliency for activating emotional perception mechanisms. The randomness-based saliency is articulated into contextual representations of the ground-object structure. Through experimental studies, the environmental saliency was demonstrated to provide a perceptual basis for the contextual identification and direct visualization of the unpredictable distribution of emotional expressions in complex scenes.

Key words: Emotional Perception; Contextual Visualization; Kansei Engineering

1 Introductory Remarks

As the result of evolution in the really existing world, human's vision system is equipped with a sophisticated information processing mechanism for understanding the scenes thronged with friendly or undesirable neighbors [1]. Through the iteration of selection pressure, simultaneously, the neighbors have developed various types of micro structures for the luminescence of emotional expressions. As intentional participants of the co-evolution process without the 'intelligent designer', human's vision seems to be able to control attention within the surroundings [2, 3], on the premise that imminent decision making should be triggered by emotional perception: dynamic identification of contextual information through early reaction to ambient light [4]. Guided by the repletion of the emotional expressions, thus, human's decision making is supervenient to the physical-geometric perspective of the surroundings. This implies that human's scope of intrinsic capability can be expanded through anticipative access to the scene to be encountered. Noticing that humans activate neuronal computation processes *prior to* the awareness of spontaneous decision making [5], the expansion of human's scope of emotional perception is required to direct attention to all possible sign patterns arising in naturally designed scenes; for instance, perception resources should be applied to possible scenes beyond the physical-geometric restriction to restore fatal perception-decision delay leading to traffic accidents [6].

Figure 1 illustrates an implementation of the enhanced maneuvering system in which the on-vehicle perceptual segments are networked with the roadway segment via state-of-the-art space infrastructure. Within such an augmentation of the scope of emotional perception, we can extend the scope of the interactive mapping scheme from in-door manufacturing spaces [7] to the satellite-roadway-vehicle network [8] as indicated in Figure 2. The system is available as the basis of anticipative road following where maneuvering processes are supported by vehicle-specific prediction of landmark objects to be encountered as well as interactive rendezvous where maneuvering processes are matched with a cut of route graph towards a contact point. Such a system is expected to augment the physical-geometric aspect of human's capability including geometric path planning [9] as well as autonomous vehicle guidance [10] beyond physical perspective; by extending the trajectory along a planned roadway, the interactive mapping system can extract an *as-is* representa-

Figure 1: Satellite-Roadway-Vehicle Integration

Figure 2: Extended Interactive Mapping Scheme

tion of the landmark objects from the bird's eye view. However, the computation time for data gathering and precise registration in the earth observation systems yields ineluctable delay between the representation of the satellite images and the distribution of temporal and/or moving objects in the scenes. Due to such a logical discrepancy, hence, the visible elements captured via anticipative access should be matched with the imminent scene through human's inherent perception process. In such a situation, direct exploitation of the *as-is* representation may yield an unexpected mental load in subsequent decision processes.

In this paper, we introduce a new framework for simulating emotional perception processes spanning over the temporal-spatio discrepancy. The problem is to 'pre-set' machine vision based on stochastic representation of not-yet-visible scenes in the bird's eye view imagery. Within the context of the interactive mapping, the complex images of the scene are articulated into a system of fractal attractors specifying symbolic descriptions of the situation. As the cue to the multi-fractal coding, we introduce a new concept called environmental saliency: a randomness-based image feature discriminating ground area and/or object patterns from distractions and/or illusions in naturally designed scenes. In what follows, two versions of latent images, scale distribution and chromatic complexity, are extracted as the observables for the generation and adaptation of the environmental saliency.

2 Randomness as the Support of Environmental Saliency

Despite the diversity of appearances, natural scenes exhibit environment-specific landmarks to be identified within the individual context of independent viewers. To focus on such a landmark object, first, the perception process should apply 'feature integration' schemes [11, 12] to 'visual saliency' randomly distributed in complex scene images [13, 14]. Next, to match the scene image with viewer-specific context, extracted saliency distribution should be articulated into a ground-object structure. In a conventional integration scheme, observed images are assumed to be structured in terms of 'sensible saliency' including contours of well-defined objects and chunks of attractive colors. However, it is well known that the concentration on 'well-defined' saliency easily incurs computational explosion in the integration of real world information. To cope with apparent diversity, in the discussion that follows, we invoke underlying scale-chromatic randomness as a latent representation of naturally designed scenes; the new problem is to extend the scope of perception to 'subconscious' aspects of the sensible saliency.

Figure 3: Scene to be analyzed

Figure 4: g_b -image of Breakdown Pixels

Perceptual Linearity: Following ecological optics, the depth of a natural scene is directly sensible based on random textures covering a connected open space as shown in Figure 3. By extracting scale information distributed in scene images, we can estimate the depth of the scene in terms of the vanishing point of scale shift. This implies that the depth of the maneuverable area y_∞ can be estimated *prior to* the identification of boundary objects. Such perceptual linearity is known to be robust imaging process [15] and available as a universal rule for analyzing naturally designed imagery.

Let f_ω be the brightness distribution in the image plane Ω . Noting that many imaging devices including the human eye detect the brightness distribution through the Gaussian point spread function, we can extract a local estimate for the scale information $\hat{\sigma}_\omega$ given by the following subcorrelation

$$\hat{\sigma}_\omega \sim \sqrt{\frac{2f_\omega}{|\Delta f_\omega|}}, \quad (1)$$

at $\omega \in \Omega$ [16]. This implies that the coherence of the perceptual linearity can be evaluated by the following measure

$$g_d(\omega|\sigma_0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\bar{\sigma}_d^2}} \exp\left[-\frac{|\hat{\sigma}_\omega - \bar{\sigma}_d|^2}{2\bar{\sigma}_d^2}\right], \quad (2a)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_d$ designates the linear scale shift model towards a vanishing point d_∞

$$\bar{\sigma}_d = \frac{\sigma_0}{d_\infty - d_0}(d_\infty - d), \quad (2b)$$

with the dominant scale of random texture σ_0 at baseline d_0 .

In a natural scene, the perceptual linearity is broken down by something perpendicular to the open space. The probability for the pixel ω to be the ‘grounding point’ of the breakdown is indexed by

$$g_b(\omega^\uparrow|\sigma_0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\hat{\sigma}_\omega^2}} \exp\left[-\frac{|\hat{\sigma}_{\omega^\uparrow} - \hat{\sigma}_\omega|^2}{2\hat{\sigma}_\omega^2}\right], \quad (3)$$

where ω^\uparrow is the upward extension of the pixel ω in the scene image; $\omega^\uparrow = (x, y + dy)$ for $\omega = (x, y) \in \Omega$ and $dy > 0$.

The coherence of the scene image with the perceptual linearity is visualized in terms of the measure g_d conditioned by the σ_0 . The support of the perceptual linearity is confined by the breakdown pixels as shown in Figure 4 where the condition σ_0 is selected as $2 \min_{\omega \in \Omega} \hat{\sigma}_\omega$ and the upward extension ω^\uparrow is aggregated into vertical chains of equi-scaled

Figure 5: Scene to be Observed

Figure 6: Complexity Reduction via ψ_ω Channel

pixels. As shown in Figures 3 and 4, we have a stochastic evaluation $\{g_a(\omega|\sigma_0), g_b(\omega^\dagger|\sigma_0)\}$ for the expansion of not-yet-identified open space in naturally designed scenes. Thus, the scale estimate $\hat{\sigma}_\omega$ is available as a randomness-based feature of ground image, i.e., an aspect of environmental saliency.

Chromatic Information Matting: The perception of chromatic diversity is essentially a mental process; *for most human observers only three primaries are required to match a test light* [17]. To simulate such a sophisticated mechanism, subtle deviation from scene-specific saliency should be exactly evaluated. For this purpose, let the diversity of the tricolor decomposition $f_\omega^{\text{RGB}} = [R_\omega \ G_\omega \ B_\omega]^T$ be indexed in R_+^3 -space with R-, G-, B-coordinates as follows

$$\phi_\omega = \phi(f_\omega^{\text{RGB}}) = \frac{f_\omega^{\text{RGB}}}{|f_\omega^{\text{RGB}}|}. \quad (4)$$

The chromatic index ϕ_ω can be applied to ‘tricolor matting’ of a complex scene as shown in Figures 5 and 6; the distribution of ϕ_ω is extracted from the scene image shown in Figure 5 to visualize the following information as shown in Figure 6:

$$\psi_\omega = f_\omega^{\text{RGB}} e^{-H(\phi_\omega)}, \quad H(\phi_\omega) = -2 \sum_{c \in \{R, G, B\}} \left(\frac{f_\omega^c}{|f_\omega^{\text{RGB}}|} \right)^2 \log \left(\frac{f_\omega^c}{|f_\omega^{\text{RGB}}|} \right).$$

These figures imply that the index ϕ_ω enhances various kinds of conspicuous landmarks in complex scene images.

Noticing that the totality of ϕ_ω is identified with the surface of the positive unit sphere ∂R_+^3 , by definition, let the diversity of chromatic information be locally evaluated in terms of the following 2D Gaussian measure

$$g_\alpha(\phi_i|\phi_j) = \frac{1}{2\pi\alpha} \exp \left[-\frac{|\phi_i - \phi_j|^2}{2\alpha} \right], \quad (5)$$

with sensitivity parameter $\alpha > 0$. Following experimental studies using roadway scenes and various natural objects including human faces, dirt bank, paved road and so on, the sensitivity factor α should be adjusted to $1/10 \sim 1/100$.

By using the probability distribution (5), we can evaluate the diversity of the chromatic saliency in terms of a palette $\mathfrak{s} = \{f_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ with the following variance

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\mathfrak{s}} &= \frac{1}{2\pi\alpha} \exp \left[-\frac{\sigma_{\phi\phi}^2}{2\alpha} \right], \\ \sigma_{\phi\phi}^2 &= \frac{1}{\|\mathfrak{s}\|(\|\mathfrak{s}\| - 1)} \times \sum_{\substack{1 \leq i, j \leq \|\mathfrak{s}\| \\ i \neq j}} |\phi(f_i) - \phi(f_j)|^2, \end{aligned}$$

where $\|(\cdot)\|$ denotes the size of the set (\cdot) . Define

$$g_\alpha(\omega|\mathfrak{s}) = g_\alpha[\phi(f_\omega)|\mathfrak{s}] = \max_{f_j \in \mathfrak{s}} g_\alpha[\phi(f_\omega)|\phi(f_j)]. \quad (6a)$$

Figure 7: Complexity Reduction via g_α -Matting

Figure 8: Random Carpet Generator

Then, we can introduce the following matching rule

$$g_\alpha(\omega|\mathfrak{s}) = g_\alpha(\phi_\omega|\mathfrak{s}) > R_{\mathfrak{s}} \Rightarrow f_\omega \stackrel{R_{\mathfrak{s}}}{\sim} \mathfrak{s}, \quad (6b)$$

for random distribution $\{\phi_\omega\}$ with scene-specific palette ‘ \mathfrak{s} ’. Figure 7 illustrates an example of saliency-based matting; in this case, the scene image is sampled via the self-similarity process partitioning and regenerating the entire image plane as shown in Figure 8; Ω is expanded towards the fixed points allocated at the four vertexes and, simultaneously, reduced into four copies of the rectangle to be filled asymptotically; the matching rule (6) is applied to the following re-coloring process $f_\omega^{\text{RGB}} \rightarrow f_i^*$ where f_i^* is the nearest sample satisfying

$$g_\alpha[\phi(f_\omega^{\text{RGB}})|\phi(f_i^*)] > \max_{f_j \in \mathfrak{s}_i^*} g_\alpha[\phi(f_\omega^{\text{RGB}})|\phi(f_j)], \quad \mathfrak{s}_i^* = \mathfrak{s} - \{f_i^*\}, \quad (7)$$

in the palette ‘ \mathfrak{s} ’. Thus, we can utilize the chromatic index ϕ_ω as randomness-based object features, i.e., as another aspect of environmental saliency. As shown in Figure 7, the environmental saliency of the scene ϕ_ω can be utilized for extracting a version of chromatic impression of naturally designed scenes as well.

3 Multi-Fractal Articulation

As demonstrated in Figures 3 4 and 7, we can extract distributions of environmental saliency ($\hat{\sigma}_\omega, \phi_\omega$) based on scale-chromatic randomness. To match with the viewer-specific context, the random distributions are required to be identified as a consistent set of connected patterns specifying an open space and articulated objects. Noticing that the nondeterministic process illustrated in Figure 8 effectively extracts scene-specific features as demonstrated in Figure 7, consider fractal coding of saliency image observed through $g_d(\omega|\sigma_0)$ -, $g_b(\omega^\dagger|\sigma_0)$ - and $g_\alpha(\phi_\omega|\mathfrak{s})$ -channels. The problem is to design a set ν of contraction mappings μ_i of the following form:

$$\mu_i(\omega) = \frac{1}{2}[\omega + \omega_{\mu_i}^f], \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, \|\nu\|, \quad (8)$$

where $\omega_{\mu_i}^f$ is the fixed point of the mapping μ_i . Such a mapping set $\nu = \{\mu_i\}$ generates a fractal attractor via the pattern dynamics as illustrated in Figure 8. By using such an explicit formulation, the expansion of a fractal attractor can be represented adding to the geometric complexity estimated via local fractal analysis [18].

g_d -image coding: Noticing that the roadway area can be segmented into skewed rectangles through perspective projection, we can identify the expansion of an open space with the fractal attractor called Sierpinski’s gasket. The gasket should cover the maximum part of the object free space without any interference with boundary objects. Let

Figure 9: Probabilistic Evaluation of Object Free Space

Figure 10: Fixed Points Based on $g_d - g_b$ -distributions

$\hat{\Omega}^f = \{ \hat{\omega}_{\mu_i}^f \}$ be the estimate of the fixed points and consider the following articulation:

$$\Lambda_i^{\mathfrak{G}} = \left\{ \lambda \in \Lambda_i \mid \left(\frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{\lambda}^T \Sigma_i^{-1} \varepsilon_{\lambda} - 1 \right) < 0 \right\}, \quad \varepsilon_{\lambda} = \lambda - \bar{\omega}_i. \quad (9)$$

In this equation, $\{ \Lambda_i \}$ denotes the following partitioning of the image plane Ω with respect to the estimate $\hat{\Omega}^f$:

$$\Lambda_i : \left\{ \omega \in \Omega \mid |\omega - \hat{\omega}_{\mu_i}^f| < |\omega - \hat{\omega}_{\mu_j}^f|, \text{ for } \hat{\omega}_{\mu_j}^f \neq \hat{\omega}_{\mu_i}^f \right\},$$

and $(\bar{\omega}_i, \Sigma_i)$ designate the first and second moments with respect to the capturing probability $\varphi_p(\omega|\nu)$ to be generated as the steady solution to the following 2D diffusion system [19]:

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_p(\omega|\nu)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{2} \Delta \varphi_p(\omega|\nu) + \rho [g_d(\omega|\sigma_0) - \varphi_p(\omega|\nu)], \quad \rho = \log_2 \|\nu\|. \quad (10)$$

The maximum spanning articulation can be designed by adjusting the estimate $\hat{\Omega}^f$ to circumscribe the articulation $\{ \Lambda_i^{\mathfrak{G}} \}$ and to avoid the chains of breakdown pixels. An example of the fractal articulation is shown in Figure 10 where the environmental saliency $(g_d(\omega|\sigma_0), g_b(\omega^\dagger|\sigma_0))$ (Figures 3 and 4) is utilized to design a gasket attractor spanning the object free space (Figure 3). The consistency of fractal articulation was verified via the following finite invariant test:

$$\Theta = \left\{ \theta \in \tilde{\Theta} \mid \exists \mu_i \in \nu : \mu_i^{-1}(\theta) \in \Theta \right\}, \quad (11)$$

where $\tilde{\Theta}$ denotes the totality of local maxima of the capturing probability $\varphi_p(\omega|\nu)$. As shown in Figure 10, the designed code generates a sufficiently large subset Θ supporting dense closed links; this implies that the object free space is represented as a connected area in the scene image.

g_α -image coding: Human vision easily articulates an unstructured distribution of the boundary objects (Figure 4) into landmark objects to be attracted. As the cue to such selective attention, suppose that a palette ‘ \mathfrak{s} ’ is extracted from a scene image with the diversity parameter $R_{\mathfrak{s}}$. Define \mathfrak{s} -object by the following subset

$$\mathfrak{D} = \left\{ \omega \in \Omega \mid f_\omega \stackrel{R_{\mathfrak{s}}}{\approx} \mathfrak{s} \right\}, \quad (12)$$

with the Laplacian-Gaussian boundary $\partial^s \mathfrak{D}$. Noticing the attractor confined by the boundary $\partial^s \mathfrak{D}$ should be expanded nondeterministically by the fixed points, we have the following allocation scheme:

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{t+1}^f &= \Omega_t^f \cup d\Omega_t^f, \\ d\Omega_t^f &= \left\{ \partial \omega^* \in \partial^s \check{\mathfrak{D}}_t \mid \bar{\eta}(\partial \omega^*, \Omega_t^f) \geq \bar{\eta}(\partial \omega, \Omega_t^f), \partial \omega \in \check{\mathfrak{D}}_t \right\}, \quad \partial^s \check{\mathfrak{D}}_t = \partial^s \mathfrak{D} - \Omega_t^f, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Figure 11: Fixed Point Allocation on $\partial^g \mathfrak{D}$

Figure 12: Articulation of Boundary Object

with respect to the following ‘semi-distance’ introduced between a point $\omega \in \Omega$ and a subset $\Lambda \subset \Omega$:

$$\bar{\eta}(\omega, \Lambda) = \max_{\lambda \in \Lambda} |\omega - \lambda|, \quad \bar{\eta}(\Lambda, \omega) = \min_{\lambda \in \Lambda} |\omega - \lambda|.$$

The expansion process (13) mutually separates the fixed points in the fixed set $\partial^g \mathfrak{D}$ and halts at the increment $d\Omega_t^f$ satisfying the following granularity condition:

$$\min_{\substack{\omega \in d\Omega_t^f \\ \lambda \in \Omega_t^f}} |\omega - \lambda| < \sigma_0. \quad (15)$$

Consider the articulation of the unstructured objects \mathfrak{D} detected as shown in Figure 11 in terms of separated fractal attractors. As the representation of the generator of one of the attractors, let v_t be the mapping set designed by the on-going allocation Ω_t^f . The connectedness of the fractal coding can be evaluated in terms of the following g_α -measure:

$$g_\alpha(f_t | \mathfrak{s}) = \min_{f \in f_t} g_\alpha(\phi(f^{\text{RGB}}) | \mathfrak{s}), \quad f_t = \left\{ f_\xi^{\text{RGB}} \mid \xi \in \Xi_t \right\}, \quad (16)$$

where Ξ_t denotes the attractor generated by v_t . Define $d\nu_t^*$ as the mapping set designed based on the set $d\Omega_t^f \cup \Omega_t^*$ where Ω_t^* designates the origin of the minimal span satisfying the following condition

$$\Omega_t^* = \left\{ \omega^* \in \Omega_t^f \mid \bar{\eta}(d\Omega_t^f, \omega^*) \leq \bar{\eta}(d\Omega_t^f, \omega_t^f) \right\}, \quad (17)$$

for arbitrary $\omega^f \in \Omega_t^f$. By using the fractal attractor $d\Xi_t^*$ associated with the fractal code $d\nu_t^*$, we have the halting condition for the expansion process (13) as follows:

$$g_\alpha(d\nu_t^* | \mathfrak{s}) < g_\alpha(f_t | \mathfrak{s}), \quad (18)$$

where $d\nu_t^*$ and f_t denote the fractal sampling associated with $d\nu_t^*$ and v_t , respectively. By applying the halting mechanism (18) to the fixed point estimates (Figure 11), the unstructured scene image is articulated into a system of ‘salient board’ wrapping landmark objects as shown in Figure 12.

Another result of the multi-fractal articulation is shown in Figures 13 and 14 where the contours of distributed balloons are observed at the pixels of discontinuity with respect to the chromatic information ϕ_ω rather than the optic array. In spite of the sensitivity to the ambient light, the scene image can be segmented via the chromatic matting as shown in Figure 13. This implies that the chromatic information ϕ_ω yields the Laplacian-Gaussian boundary within the expansion of the object images to be articulated into a cluster of fixed points; in this case, five points on the Laplacian-Gaussian boundary are selected as the maximum connected set of the fixed points associated with a possible fractal attractor spanning an equi-chromatic domain.

Figure 13: Fractal Matting

Figure 14: Multi-Fractal Articulation

Figure 15: Fractal Sampling of a Scene

Figure 16: $g_d - g_\alpha$ Equivalence

4 Perceptual Equivalence

As shown in Figures 3, 4 and 6, the scale and chromatic aspects of the environmental saliency can be extracted through the bottom up processes (2)+ (3) and (6), respectively. By identifying the joint distribution $\{g_d(\omega|\sigma_0), g_b(\omega^\dagger|\sigma_0)\}$ with the invariant measure to be generated through the self-similarity process shown in 8, we have a design of fractal model spanning over a connected object free space. This implies that the scale aspect of the environmental saliency induces a focusing mechanism in a not-yet-structured scene image and supervenient control process going through the open space as well.

On the other hand, by applying the self-similarity process governed by the contraction mappings (8) to the entire image plane, we can efficiently control the sampling mechanism of the chromatic aspect of the environmental saliency as illustrated in Figure 7. Thus, we can concentrate computational resources to the distribution $g_\alpha(\omega|\mathfrak{s})$ conditioned by a pre-assigned palette ' \mathfrak{s} '. Being masked by a palette color $f_i^* \in \mathfrak{s}$, in fact, the images of landmark objects are extracted from an unstructured scene image as well and confined by the Laplacian-Gaussian boundaries on which the successive expansion process (13) allocates a set of fixed points as shown in Figure 14.

Such an attention-generation scheme based on unstructured imagery $(\hat{\sigma}_\omega, \phi_\omega)$ is expected to play a crucial role in the implementation of human-readable computer vision. To establish the theoretical basis for the computer implementation, in the discussion that follows, we discuss the consistency of the saliency information within the context of human and/or machine perception: *under what conditions, can the saliency information $(\hat{\sigma}_\omega, \phi_\omega)$ support essentially equivalent fractal articulation of the scene?*

Ground Driven Perception: Figures 15 and 16 show a part of experimental results for machine perception of a connected open space in a scene (Figure 3). In this experiment, the distributions $\{g_d(\omega|\sigma_0), g_b(\omega^\dagger|d_0)\}$ are generated

Figure 17: Multi-Fractal Coding

Figure 18: Finite Invariance Test on g_d -Distribution

Figure 19: Multi-Fractal Coding

Figure 20: Finite Invariance Test on g_d -Distribution

as the cue to the design of a fractal code ν (Figure 4) consistent with the object free space (Figure 10). This implies that we can utilize the mapping set ν for generating the palette ‘ \mathfrak{s} ’ of the open space as shown in Figure 15. The resulting $g_\alpha(\omega|\mathfrak{s})$ -mating of the scene image is indicated in Figure 16. As shown in this figure, the $g_\alpha(\omega|\mathfrak{s})$ -mating process can regenerate a distribution sufficiently similar to $g_d(\omega|\sigma_0)$. In addition, the mapping set adapted to the $g_\alpha(\omega|\mathfrak{s})$ -mating yields sufficient invariant links through the finite invariant test (11) as shown in Figure 16. Thus, the consistency of the fractal code ν is maintained through the chromatic adaptation process.

Object-Driven Perception Perceptual equivalence has been demonstrated in the reverse procedure where $g_\alpha(\omega|\mathfrak{s})$ -distribution is used as the startup signal. Experimental results are summarized in Figures 17 – 20. In these cases, saliency colors in the matted images, shown in Figures 7 and 13, are selected by a human operator; the pixels with chromatic similarity are collected and articulated as illustrated in Figures 17 and 19 where pointed objects are identified with two sets of contraction mappings, respectively. The fractal codes consistent with the g_α -distribution were applied to the another aspect of saliency, $\hat{\sigma}_\omega$ -distribution, to yield sufficient invariant links in the $g_b(\omega^\dagger|\sigma_0)$ -areas as shown in Figures 18 and 20, respectively. In these evaluations, the scale space model $\bar{\sigma}_d$ was identified via the fractal sampling of the scene images (Figures 17 and 19, respectively). Thus, we can exploit chromatic saliency as the cue to the identification of boundary objects consistently with the detection of an open space based on scale saliency.

5 Contextual Visualization

The effectiveness of the environmental saliency on the contextual scene analysis was demonstrated through experimental studies. Figure 21 displays results of contextual analysis where the ground-object structure is identified and visualized on the matted version of the scene image (a); the left side of the boundary objects is articulated to confine an area of a post office as shown in (b) where a sign board is also articulated but eliminated from the objects to be visualized. This result implies that a version of emotional expression concerning the values and/or special taste, required for driving an

(a) Complexity Reduction via g_α -matting

(b) Multi-Fractal Articulation

Figure 21: Be Careful of Traffic Gateway: an Expression of Values and/or Special Taste

(a) Complexity Reduction via g_α -matting

(b) Multi-Fractal Articulation

Figure 22: Be Careful of Protruding Post: an Expression of Space and Movement

(a) Complexity Reduction via g_α -matting

(b) Multi-Fractal Articulation

Figure 23: Be Careful of Crossing Car: an Expression of Fear

intelligent vehicle [20], can be identified as the environmental saliency in complex scenes.

Other results are shown in Figures 22 and 23 where a protruding post and a crossing car are identified as objects to notice for pedestrians and vehicles going through the roadways, respectively. These results imply that we can exploit the fractal articulation scheme as the detector of emotional expressions introduced in the evolution scenario of the Braitenberg's intelligent vehicles.

As shown in Figures 21 – 23, we can concentrate the computational resources for the detection of various types of emotional expressions in naturally complex scenes where attractants should be designed to evoke the $g_\alpha(\omega|s)$ -matting channel. Being supported by such emotional perceptants, the designed fractal codes are formally matchable with the viewer specific context. Noticing that the Braitenberg's vehicles develop mental functionalities to be grounded on the real world, we can simulate a part of the human's neuronal computation steps by the multi-fractal coding process on the scale-chromatic aspects of the environmental saliency.

Figure 24: Perceptual Equivalence

Figure 25: Multi-Aspect Visualization

6 Implementation and Discussions

Based on the saliency based approach, a scene analysis system was implemented on the satellite-roadway-vehicle network. In this implementation, the image features $(\hat{\sigma}_d, \phi_\omega)$, are extracted via locally parallel scheme (1)+(4) to generate scale-chromatic aspects of the environmental saliency via pixel wise estimator (2)+(5); the multi-aspect representation is available as the dynamic support of multi-fractal articulation process (10)+(13) and, simultaneously, the performance indices of internal and external control parameters (σ_0, Ξ) and (ω_∞, ϕ_i) , respectively. Due to the asymptotic stability of the dynamical system (10), the finite set Θ rapidly converges on the transient field $\varphi_p(\omega|v)$. By combining monotone manipulation (13) on a small boundary set $\partial^g \mathcal{D}$, hence, we can apply the multi-fractal articulation process to on-vehicle camera imagery without an auxiliary timing control device. In this implementation, thus, we have a cooperation architecture for *in-situ* integration of the environmental saliency as shown in Figure 24. The system accepts a couple of cue points (ω_∞, ϕ_i) in the scene image to instantiate the environmental saliency. As the observables of the randomness distributed in the naturally designed scenes, the saliency is jointly articulated into a multi-fractal representation of the ground-object structure. Based on the randomness spanning the scene images, environmental saliency is available as a perceptual equivalence for jointly identifying the viewer-specific context.

Figure 25 illustrates an example of multi-aspect visualization within the framework of anticipative road following. In this case, the scene is articulated into ground and boundary areas to visualize a maneuvering context: the confirmation of a roadway area as an object free space with annotation of boundary objects out of the confirmed lane (Vehicle Segment) and anticipative expansion of the roadway area towards a crossing beyond the viewer's perspective (Roadway Segment). In contrast with conventional vehicle information systems implemented for global navigation and autonomous control, the visualizations are mutually associated through the internal information structure: the environmental saliency where projected aspects maintain consistency via dynamics of perceptual equivalence. For instance, the direction of an extended roadway pattern is downloaded to preset the on-vehicle vision; the palette gathered through the fractal sampling of the object free area is uploaded to dispatch a robotic vehicle in the satellite image. Such a decentralized organization scheme provides a reflective interface to a multitude of participants of the maneuvering process including vehicles in the same cut of the bird's eye view, authority of the traffic control systems and navigators. The key technologies for the implementation of the multi-aspect representation can be applied to the extension of perceptual basis in the kansei engineering. The design and the performance of the context visualization process should be indexed within the framework of the kansei engineering, in turn.

7 Concluding Remarks

A saliency-based scheme was introduced for contextual analysis of naturally designed scenes. We can implement an emotional perception channel to control the attention of on-vehicle vision system. The resulting description of the scene structure is transferable as a robust prediction for emotional expressions through the satellite-roadway-vehicle network. Through experimental studies, the saliency-based scene analysis was demonstrated to provide a computational basis for the identification and the visualization of *in situ* maneuvering context. The evaluation of human's acceptance of the context visualization is the next step. The integration of human and machine perception within the framework of the kansei engineering is left to future investigations.

8 References

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